

“Involta” Ilmiy Jurnalni

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Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna

Toshkent Davlat Iqtisodiyot universiteti tadqiqotchisi

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada brend kapitali tushunchasining mohiyati, rivojlanish evolyutsiyasi va nazariy asoslari yoritilib, muallif tomonidan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.*

К

а **Аннотация:** *В статье описывается сущность концепции капитала Бренда, эволюция развития и теоретические основы, а также разрабатываются рекомендации автора.*

t **Ключевые слова:** *бренд, управление маркетингом, вузы, бренд-капитал.*

Annotation: *The article describes the essence of the concept of brand capital, the evolution of development and the theoretical basis, and developed recommendations by the author.*

' **Keywords:** *brand, marketing management, universities, brand capital.*

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Identifikatsion yondashuv (1990-yillar o'rtalari) – kompaniya o'zining

Shaxsiylashtirishga qaratilgan yondashuv (1997) – D. Aakerning «Brend

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O'zaro munosabatlarga asoslangan yondashuv esa 1998 yilda shakllangan bo'lib, tadqiqot S.Furnьe «Brendlar va ularning iste'molchilar o'rtasidagi o'zaro

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Davr	Brend kontseptsiyasining mohiyati	Avtor va yaratgan yili
		Markuard: 1965
		Smit: 1956, Yankilovich: 1964, Mayner va Slater: 1964, Shet: 1967
		Цуннинхам: 1956
		Kotler va Zальtman: 1971

¹ Aaker, J. L. Dimensions of Brand Personality. Journal of Marketing Research (JMR); Aug 1997, Vol. 34 Issue 3, p347-356

² Anders Hampf & Kirsti Lindberg-Repo, Branding: The Past, Present, and Future: A Study of the Evolution and Future of Branding

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Olimlarning <i>brendni ishlab chiquvchi kompaniyalar</i> uchun qiymat yaratishga qaratilgan yondashuvlari	Olimlarning <i>brendni iste'molchilar</i> uchun qiymat yaratishga qaratilgan yondashuvlari
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³ Holt, D B Why do brands cause trouble? A dialectical theory of consumer culture and branding Journal of Consumer Research, June 2002 (29), p 70-90; Holt, D B How Brands become Icons The Principles of Cultural Branding, Boston MA 2004 Harvard Business School

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⁴ Е.Б. Шведина; Товарный знак и бренд: семантика понятий и ее значения в управлении брендом; Южный федеральный университет, г. Ростов-на-Дону; 2011.

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lozim deb xorijiy adabiyotlarda ta'kidlanadi. Bunda o'z-o'zidan ko'rinib turibdi, tovar belgisi – brend belgisiga, savdo nomi – brend nomiga va umuman savdo markasi

3- rasm. Savdo markasining elementlari ⁶

Umuman olganda, brend kategoriyasi turli tadqiqot sohalari – marketing,

⁶

Карпова С.В., Современный брендинг, монография, Москва, 2011

ga misol sifatida portugaliyalik Krishtiano Ronaldo brendini qarash mumkin. Uning sportchilik faoliyati natijasida bir necha xalqaro e'tiroflarga ega bo'lganligi "Ronaldo" brendining vujudga kelishiga xizmat qildi. Masalan, Taym jurnali 2014

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1. Brend – bu iste'molchilar ongida yashaydigan obraz va g'oyadir. Bu –

'rsatish belgisi esa – xizmatlar brendini himoya qiladi. Tovar belgisi iste'molchilar

8

Fikrimizcha, brend kapitali bu – ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonadan tomonidan

Brend identifikatsiyasi termini inglizchadan "brand identity" so'zidan olingan bo'lib, rus adabiyotlarida ham "brendovaya identika" yoki "brendovaya identifikatsiya" deb keltiriladi. Shu bois dissertatsiyada brend identifikatsiyasi deb

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⁸ Шведина, Екатерина Борисовна Функциональные возможности инструментария современного маркетинга в бренде и управлении брендом : диссертация ... кандидата экономических наук : 08.00.05 Ростов-на-Дону 2013

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